

BASING THE PARAMETERS OF THE BODY OF THE MACHINE THAT PREPARES THE SOIL FOR PLANTING VEGETABLES AND POTATOES

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Abstract. *In the world, the leading place is occupied by the development and use of energy-saving and high-performance machines for soil cultivation and preparation for sowing. "If we take into account that on a global scale, the area of land sown with potatoes is 22 million hectares". In particular, in this direction, it is relevant to carry out targeted scientific research on the development of a combined machine and the rationale for the technological process of its working bodies, ensuring resource saving in the processes of interaction with the soil. A half-screw body was chosen as a pusher shaper of the machine that prepares the soil for planting potatoes, and its parameters were theoretically and experimentally justified. The basic principles and methods of classical mechanics, mathematical analysis and statistics were used in this study. According to the results of theoretical and experimental studies, in order to ensure the required level of foam formation with low energy consumption, the cover width of the body should be 200 mm, the minimum height of its tipper and column should be 330 mm and 560 mm, and the length of the tipper wing should be in the range of 515-545 mm.*

Key words: *comb former, body, soil, dump, corps wing, agrotechnical and energetic indicators of the device.*

ОСНОВАНИЕ ПАРАМЕТРОВ КОРПУСА МАШИНЫ, ПОДГОТОВЛЯЮЩЕЙ ПОЧВУ ПОД ПОСАДКУ ОВОЩЕЙ И КАРТОФЕЛЯ

Аннотация. *В мире ведущее место занимает разработка и применение энерго-ресурсосберегающих и высокопроизводительных машин для обработки почвы и подготовки её к посеву. «Если учесть, что в мировом масштабе площадь земель посева картофеля составляет 22 млн. гектаров»¹, то важной задачей считается разработка энерго-ресурсосберегающих технологий и машин с высоким качеством работы и производительности для подготовки почвы к посеву картофеля. «Если учесть, что в мировом масштабе площадь земель, засеянных картофелем, составляет 22 млн га». В частности, в этом направлении актуальным является проведение целевых научных исследований по разработке комбинированной машины и обоснованию технологического процесса ее рабочих органов, обеспечивающих ресурсосбережение в процессах взаимодействия с почвой. В качестве толкателя-формирователя машины, подготавливающей почву под посадку картофеля, выбран полувинтовой корпус, теоретически и экспериментально обоснованы его параметры. В работе использовались основные принципы и методы классической механики, математического анализа и статистики. По результатам теоретических и экспериментальных исследований, для обеспечения необходимого уровня пенообразования при малых энергозатратах ширина захвата корпуса должна быть 200 мм, минимальная высота его отвала и корпуса должна быть 330 мм и 560 мм, а длине крыла отвала должна быть в пределах 515-545 мм.*

¹ <http://docplayer.ru>, <http://www.rosinformagrotech.ru>

Ключевые слова: гребнеобразователь, корпус, почва, отвал, корпусное крыло, агротехнические и энергетические показатели устройства.

1. Introduction. In the world, the development and use of energy-saving and high-performance working bodies for preparing the soil for planting at the same time takes a leading place. At the same time, great attention is being paid to the creation of machines that perform all the technological processes of preparing the potatoes for planting by cultivating the soil, forming the tubers, in one pass through the field.

Researches on the creation and use of plow forming machines with tillage, theoretical and experimental justification of the parameters of their working bodies V.I.Kurdyumov [5], Sharonov, B.C. [6] Lakhmakov[7], F.M. Mamatov[3, 4], B.S. Mirzayev[2] and Kodirov [1] others.

However, in these researches, the justification of the theoretical and experimental parameters, which ensure the high quality of work with low energy consumption, while cultivating the soil for planting potatoes, has not been fully studied.

2. Methods and results. The basic principles and methods of classical mechanics, mathematical analysis and statistics were used in this study.

Theoretical and experimental studies were carried out to justify the parameters of the casings of the machine that prepares the soil for planting potatoes in one pass of the field. As a result, the construction scheme of machine bodies implementing the technology of preparing soil for planting potatoes was developed (Fig. 1). It consists of column 1, tipper 2, harrow 3, guide blade 4.

We determine the parameters of the core forming bodies based on the main process of core formation during machine operation.

Basing the parameters of the box forming body. The main function of the machine's right and left-turning bodies is to form the initial pile. As a furrow former, a semi-screw body was chosen because it turns the soil well and pushes it to the side relatively little.

Figure 1. The main parameters of the hull forming the furrow: 1 – a column; 2 – tipper; 3 – ploughshare; 4 – guide knife

The following are the main parameters of the housing that affect the quality and energy performance indicators (Fig. 1): body height H_m ; coverage width of the corpus b_κ ; body tipper height and width H_κ and $b_{\kappa a}$; the angle of entry of the ploughshare into the soil ε ; the angle of installation of the ploughshare relative to the wall of the egate γ_n ; angle of inclination relative to the base of the plow blade τ .

We determine the main parameters of the body in terms of the formation of the chest of the required shape and height in the theoretical justification. According to the results of research conducted by a number of scientists, we accept the shape of the initially formed cross-section of the breast as sinusoidal (Fig. 2). This pattern is equal to the specified row spacing B_M from both ends of the width b_1 кенгликдаги and a thick slabs should be cut and turned opposite to each other in the middle. Then the minimum coverage width of the case will be as follows

$$b_{\kappa \min} = \frac{B_M}{4}. \quad (1)$$

(1) according to the expression, $b_{\kappa \min} = 17,5$ cm when the row spacing for planting potatoes is 70 cm wide. Taking into account the unevenness of the field terrain and the vibrations of the machine in the horizontal plane

We determine the processing depth of the hull from the condition that the overturned blade is stable, that is, it does not roll back.

$$a \leq \frac{b_\kappa}{1,27} = 15,75 \text{ cm}. \quad (2)$$

In this case, the processing depth along the edge of the casing

$$a_\rho = a - \frac{1}{2} b_\kappa \text{tg} \tau. \quad (3)$$

(3) according to the expression, when $b_\kappa = 20$ cm and $\tau = 6^\circ$, the maximum processing depth of the case is $a_{\max} = 14.7$ cm. In the process of turning, the volume of the soil increases. When this situation is considered $a_{\max} = 0,76$, $b_\kappa = 15,2$ cm.

Figure 2. Scheme for determining the coverage width of the body

Taking into account the above, we accept the processing depth of the case as $a = 15$ cm.

Basing the body tipper height. To determine the height of the body tipper, we see 4 tipping processes under the influence of the body and the guide knife.

Due to the fact that the rolling process of the blade is carried out under closed cutting conditions and the edges are deformed during this process, its shape changes. Under the influence of the tipper and guide blade, the plowshare, which is cut from the bottom of the plow, rotates and rises about its center of gravity almost without sideways movement until its edge D touches the edge of the field. Then D is rolled around the edge and placed on the surface of the field. According to Figure 3, OE is at the top when it is perpendicular to the field surface, i.e. OX. Taking into account the above, we determine the height of the tipper

$$H_a = a + OE = a + \sqrt{a^2 + (b_n - \Delta_n^2)}, \quad (4)$$

where b_n – is the width of the palm, $b_\kappa = b_n$;

Δ_n – the width of the deformed part of the blade, cm.

(4) to expression $a = 15$ cm, $\Delta_n = 10$ cm and $b_\kappa = 20$ cm put $H_a = 33$ cm we determine that it should be.

We determine the height of the body according to the following formula, provided that the blade passes freely under the frame and does not clog it with plant residues and soil.

$$H_m = 1,25H_a. \quad (5)$$

Putting the value of H_a according to (4) to (5), we get the following

$$H_m = 1,25[a + \sqrt{a^2 + (b_n - \Delta_n^2)}]. \quad (6)$$

Figure 3. Scheme of overturning of the soil slab under the influence of the body

For bodies working in closed cutting conditions, its height is increased to the processing depth, i.e

$$H_\kappa = 2,25a + 1,25\sqrt{a^2 + (b_\kappa - \Delta_n^2)}. \quad (7)$$

Putting $a = 15$ cm and $b_\kappa = 20$ cm in the expression (8), we determine that the minimum height of the body should be $H_\kappa = 56.25$ cm.

On the basis of the technological parameters of the casing defined above, it is possible to determine the shape and cross-sectional surface (S) of the blade it processes. (Fig. 3, a). The mutual equality of the cross-sectional surfaces of right- and left-turning blades ($S_y = S_u$) we determine the cross-sectional surface and the center of gravity of the right-turning plane. The cross-sectional surface of the shell processed by the body consists of a rectangle and a triangle.

According to Fig. 2, the general surface of the cross-section of the hull is processed

$$S_{ym} = S_1 + S_2, \quad (8)$$

Correspondingly, the surfaces of quadrilateral $ABCD$ and triangular OIC are S_1 and S_2

$$S_1 = (a - b_n \operatorname{tg} \delta) b_n, \quad (9)$$

$$S_2 = \frac{1}{2} b_\kappa^2 \operatorname{tg} \delta. \quad (10)$$

Putting the values of S_1 and S_2 according to (9) and (10) into (8), we get the following result

$$S_{yM} = ab_k - \frac{1}{2}b_k^2 \operatorname{tg} \tau. \quad (11)$$

3. Results and Discussion

Experimental studies were carried out in order to verify the results of the theoretical studies and to determine the parameters of the machine that prepares the soil for planting potatoes, which ensure the quality of work at the required level with low energy consumption. For this purpose, left- and right-turning types of housings were made (Fig. 5).

Experimental studies were conducted in order to study the effect of the length of the body tippers on the performance of the device. For conducting experiments, flippers with a wing length of 485, 515, 545 and 575 mm were prepared (Figure 6). The speed of the aggregate is 6-9 km/h, the working depth is 15 cm, and the longitudinal distance between the bodies is 400 mm.

Figure 4. A scheme for determining the cross-sectional area and center of gravity of the hull

When the length of the wing of the body increases from 485 to 575 mm at both speeds of the working bodies of the device, the length of the wing of the pusher is $\ell = 575$ mm (1), $\ell = 545$ mm (2), $\ell = 515$ mm (3) $\ell = 485$ mm (4) flippers that are the height of the profile (H) first increased and then decreased according to the law of the bubble parabola.

a) – housing that flips to the left; б) – housing that flips to the right

Figure 5. The bodies that make up the powder

This is due to the change in the distance of the particles of soil coming out of the wing. At

small values of the wing length (less than 500 mm), the main part of the soil particles is thrown to a small distance and does not fall into the center of the forming pile. At large values of the wing length (greater than 545 mm), the main part of the soil particles is thrown far, that is, at a distance greater than half the distance between the bodies. As a result, the height of the breast is reduced. At the values of the wing length in the range of 515-545 mm, a wing of the required height is formed.

Figure 6. Tumblers prepared for conducting experiments

At both speeds, when the wing length of the hulls increased from 485 to 575 mm, the fraction of soil erosion increased according to the parabolic law, that is, the amount of fractions smaller than 50 mm in size increased.

This can be explained by the fact that the time of interaction with the soil overturning increases with the shortening of the blade length.

At values of wing length less than 515 mm, the level of soil compaction does not satisfy agrotechnical requirements.

At both speeds, the drag of the hulls increased proportionally in a straight line as the wing length increased. This can be explained by increasing the frictional forces on the soil overturning as the wing length increases.

Thus, the agrotechnical and energetic performance of the device directly depends on the length of the body tipper wing, and this distance should be in the range of 515-545 mm in order to perform the technological process with high quality of work with low energy consumption.

4. Conclusions.

1. The working body of the punching machine is semi-spiral right- and left-turning housings, the working surfaces of which are directed towards each other and are arranged in pairs in the longitudinal plane, which ensures the required quality of work with low energy consumption.

2. According to the results of the theoretical studies, in order to ensure the required level of foam formation with low energy consumption, the body type is semi-screw, the width of the body is 200 mm, and the minimum height of its tip and column should be 330 mm and 560 mm.

3. According to the results of experimental studies, the length of the body tipper wing should be in the range of 515-545 mm in order to perform the technological process with high quality of work with low energy consumption.

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